

Matutini, F., Baudry, J., Pain, G., Sineau, M. and Pithon, J. (2020) How citizen science could improve Species Distribution Models and their independent assessment. bioRxiv, 2020.06.02.129536, ver. 4 peer-reviewed and recommended by PCI Ecology. doi: 10.1101/2020.06.02.129536
Access for biological data

Data used in the paper Matutini et al. 2020 have been collected by few hundreds of observers and some professional structures. For data access, please contact database coordinators (see below).

Opportunistic presence data (calibration and cross-validation dataset)

General coordination of the regional Atlas of amphibians: Ligue pour la Protection des Oiseaux – Pays-de-la-Loire (<http://paysdelaloire.lpo.fr/>).

Contact : Benoît MARCHADOUR - benoit.marchadour@lpo.fr

File name: Matutini-et-al_2020_data_atlas_presence_only.csv

Exemple file in Zenodo: Matutini-et-al_2020_data_atlas_presence_only_sample.csv

Standardised detection-nondetection data (external validation dataset)

Name of the citizen science program: “Un Dragon dans mon Jardin”

Coordination: URCPIE – “Union régionale des centres d’initiatives pour l’environnement »

Contact: Morgane SINEAU - msineau@cpie72.fr

File name: Matutini-et-al_2020_data_external_validation.csv

Exemple file in Zenodo: Matutini-et-al_2020_data_external_validation_sample.csv